

Robust Adaptive Model Tracking Control for Linear Infinite Dimensional Symmetric Hyperbolic Systems

Mark J. Balas, *Fellow, IEEE* and Susan A. Frost, *Member, IEEE*

Abstract—Symmetric Hyperbolic Systems of partial differential equations describe many physical phenomena such as wave behavior, electromagnetic fields, and quantum fields. The plant is described by a closed densely defined linear operator that generates a continuous semigroup of bounded operators on the Hilbert space of states. Here we show that there exists a stabilizing direct model reference adaptive control law with certain disturbance rejection and robustness properties. The closed loop system is shown to be exponentially convergent to a neighborhood with radius proportional to bounds on the size of the disturbance. We apply the results to control of symmetric hyperbolic systems with coercive boundary conditions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many control systems are inherently infinite dimensional when they are described by partial differential equations. Currently there is renewed interest in the control of these kinds of systems especially in flexible aerospace structures and the quantum control field [1]-[2]. It is especially of interest to control these systems adaptively via finite-dimensional controllers. In our work [3]-[6] we have accomplished direct model reference adaptive control and disturbance rejection with very low order adaptive gain laws for MIMO finite dimensional systems. When systems are subjected to an unknown internal delay, these systems are also infinite dimensional in nature. The adaptive control theory can be modified to handle this situation [7]. However, this approach does not handle the situation when partial differential equations describe the open loop system.

Our focus here will be upon Symmetric Hyperbolic Systems of partial differential equations. Such systems, originated by K.O. Friedrichs and P. D. Lax, describe many physical phenomena such as wave behavior, electromagnetic fields, and the theory of relativistic quantum fields; for example, see [15]-[18]. Other references to details of symmetric hyperbolic systems appear in [12]-[14]. To illustrate the utility of the adaptive control law, we apply the results to control of symmetric hyperbolic systems with coercive boundary conditions.

This paper considers the effect of infinite dimensionality on the adaptive control approach of [4]-[6]. We will show that the adaptively controlled system is globally stable, but the adaptive error is no longer guaranteed to approach the origin. However, exponential convergence to a neighborhood

M.J. Balas is with the Aerospace Engineering Department, Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University, Daytona Beach, FL 32114 USA (balasm@erau.edu).

S.A. Frost is with the Intelligent Systems Division, NASA Ames Research Center, Moffett Field, CA 94035 USA (susan.frost@nasa.gov).

can be achieved as a result of the control design. We will prove a robustness result for the adaptive control which extends the results of [22] to handle robust tracking of a finite dimensional model and mitigate persistent disturbances.

II. SYMMETRIC HYPERBOLIC SYSTEMS

Our focus here will be upon robust adaptive controller on the following m input, m output Symmetric Hyperbolic Problem:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial x}{\partial t} = Ax + B(u + u_D) + v \\ y = Cx \equiv \begin{bmatrix} (c_1, x) \\ (c_2, x) \\ (c_3, x) \\ \dots \\ (c_m, x) \end{bmatrix} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

with inner product $(v, w) \equiv \int_{\Omega} (v^T w) dz$ and Ω is a bounded open set with smooth boundary, and where

$$B \equiv \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ b_3 \\ \dots \\ b_m \end{bmatrix} : \mathfrak{R}^m \rightarrow X \text{ linear}; b_i \in D(A),$$

$x(0) \equiv x_0 \in D(A) \subseteq X \equiv L^2_N(\Omega)$, and

$$C : X \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}^m \text{ linear}; c_i \in D(A).$$

Now we define the closed linear operator A with domain $D(A)$ dense in the Hilbert space $X \equiv L^2(\Omega)$ with inner product $(v_1, v_2) \equiv \int_{\Omega} (v_1^T v_2) dz$ as:

$$Ax \equiv \sum_{i=1}^N A_i \frac{\partial x}{\partial z_i} + A_0 x$$

where A_i are $N \times N$ symmetric constant matrices, A_0 is a real $N \times N$ constant matrix, and x is an $N \times 1$ column vector of functions.

Thus (1) is a symmetric Hyperbolic System of first order partial differential equations with

$$A(\xi) \equiv \sum_{i=1}^N \xi_i A_i$$

which is an NxN symmetric matrix [15]. The Boundary Conditions which define the operator domain $D(A)$ will be *coercive*, i.e. $h^T n = 0$ where

$$h(x) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} x^T A_1 x & x^T A_2 x & x^T A_3 x & \dots & x^T A_N x \end{bmatrix} \text{ and}$$

$n(z)$ is the outward normal vector on boundary $\partial\Omega$ of the domain $\Omega \subseteq \mathfrak{R}^N$.

In order to accomplish disturbance rejection in a direct adaptive scheme, we will make use of a definition, given in [7], for persistent disturbances:

Definition 2: A disturbance vector $u_D \in R^q$ is said to be **persistent** if it satisfies the **disturbance generator equations**:

$$\begin{cases} u_D(t) = \theta z_D(t) \\ \dot{z}_D(t) = F z_D(t) \end{cases} \text{ or } \begin{cases} u_D(t) = \theta z_D(t) \\ z_D(t) = L \phi_D(t) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where F is a marginally stable matrix and $\phi_D(t)$ is a vector of known functions forming a basis for all the possible disturbances. This is known as “a disturbance with known waveform but unknown amplitudes”.

The *objective of control* in this paper will be to cause the output $y(t)$ of the plant to asymptotically track the output $y_m(t)$ of a linear finite-dimensional **Reference Model**:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_m = A_m x_m + B_m u_m \\ y_m = C_m x_m; x_m(0) = x_0^m \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where the **reference model state** $x_m(t)$ is an N_m -dimensional vector with **reference model output** $y_m(t)$ having the *same* dimension as the plant output $y(t)$. In general, the plant and reference models need *not* have the same dimensions. The excitation of the reference model is accomplished via the vector $u_m(t)$ which is generated by

$$\dot{u}_m = F_m u_m; u_m(0) = u_0^m \quad (4)$$

The reference model parameters (A_m, B_m, C_m, F_m) will be completely known.

We define the **output error vector**

$$e_y \equiv y - y_m \xrightarrow{t \rightarrow \infty} N(0, r) \quad (5)$$

And our goal is not to necessarily drive the error to zero, but to a small neighborhood of zero. This control objective will be accomplished by a direct **Adaptive Control Law** of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} u &= G_m x_m + G_u u_m + G_e e_y + G_D \phi_D \\ &= G_e e_y + G_\eta \eta; \quad \eta \equiv \begin{bmatrix} \phi_D \\ x_m \\ u_m \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

III. IDEAL TRAJECTORIES

We define the **Ideal Trajectories** for (1) in the following way:

$$\begin{cases} x_* = S_{11}^* x_m + S_{12}^* u_m + S_{13}^* z_D = S_1 z \\ u_* = S_{21}^* x_m + S_{22}^* u_m + S_{23}^* z_D = S_2 z \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

with $z \equiv \begin{bmatrix} x_m \\ u_m \\ z_d \end{bmatrix} \in \mathfrak{R}^L$

where the **ideal trajectory** $x_*(t)$ is generated by the **ideal control** $u_*(t)$ from

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial x_*}{\partial t} = A x_* + B u_* + \Gamma u_D \\ y_* = C x_* = y_m \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

If such ideal trajectories exist, they will be linear combinations of the reference model state, disturbance state, and reference model input, and they will produce exact output tracking in a disturbance-free plant.

From (7) we obtain the **Model Matching Conditions**:

$$\begin{cases} A S_1 + B S_2 = S_1 L_m + H_1 \\ C S_1 = H_2 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &\equiv [S_{11}^* \quad S_{12}^* \quad S_{13}^*]: \mathfrak{R}^L \rightarrow D(A) \subset X, \\ S_2 &\equiv [S_{21}^* \quad S_{22}^* \quad S_{23}^*]: \mathfrak{R}^L \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}^m, \\ L_m &\equiv \begin{bmatrix} A_m & B_m & 0 \\ 0 & F_m & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & F \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and } \begin{cases} H_1 \equiv [0 \quad 0 \quad -\Gamma \theta] \\ H_2 \equiv [C_m \quad 0 \quad 0] \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Because (S_1, S_2) are both of finite rank, they are bounded linear operators on their respective domains.

Now we have the following theorem on the *Existence of Ideal Trajectories* [21]:

Theorem 1: Assume CB is nonsingular. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(L_m) &= \sigma(A_m) \cup \sigma(F_m) \cup \sigma(F) \\ &\subset \rho(\bar{A}_{22}) \equiv \{\lambda \in C / (\lambda I - \bar{A}_{22})^{-1} : l_2 \rightarrow l_2, \\ &\text{is a bounded linear operator}\} \end{aligned}$$

(or $\sigma(L_m) \cap \sigma(\bar{A}_{22}) = \emptyset$ where $\sigma(\bar{A}_{22}) \equiv [\rho(\bar{A}_{22})]^c$)

if and only if

there exist unique bounded linear operator solutions

(S_1, S_2) satisfying the Matching Conditions.

For this application we will assume *the disturbances are step functions*. Note that the disturbance functions can be any basis function as long as φ_D is bounded, in particular sinusoidal disturbances are often applicable. So we have

$$\varphi_D \equiv 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{cases} \dot{u}_D = (1)z_D \\ \dot{z}_D = (0)z_D \end{cases} \quad \text{which implies } F = 0 \quad \text{and}$$

$$\theta_D = 1.$$

IV. ROBUST ADAPTIVE CONTROL LAW

Now we define the state tracking error $e \equiv x - x_*$ which

$$\text{implies that } \begin{cases} \frac{\partial e}{\partial t} = Ae + B\Delta u \\ \Delta y = Ce = y - y_m = e_y \end{cases}$$

where $\Delta u = u - u_*$

The direct adaptive controller (6) will have adaptive gains given by:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{G}_u = -e_y u_m^* \gamma_u - aG_u; \gamma_u > 0 \\ \dot{G}_m = -e_y x_m^* \gamma_m - aG_m; \gamma_m > 0 \\ \dot{G}_e = -e_y e_y^* \gamma_e - aG_e; \gamma_e > 0 \\ \dot{G}_D = -e_y \phi_D^* \gamma_D - aG_D; \gamma_D > 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Now use

$$u = G_e y + G_D \phi_D = G_e^* y + G_D^* \phi_D + \Delta G_D \eta \quad \text{where}$$

$$\eta \equiv \begin{bmatrix} y \\ \phi_D \end{bmatrix}$$

which implies

$$x_t = \underbrace{[Ax + BG_e^* Cx]}_{A_c x} + Bw + v$$

which implies

$$A_c = A + BG_e^* C.$$

Since the boundary conditions are coercive, we use the Divergence Theorem to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (A_c x, x) &= (Ax, x) + (BG_e^* Cx, x) \\ &= \int_{\Omega} (x^T \sum_{i=1}^N A_i \frac{\partial x}{\partial z_i}) dz + (A_0 x, x) + (BG_e^* Cx, x) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\text{Div}(h)} (\nabla \circ h) dz + (A_0 x, x) + (BG_e^* Cx, x) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} (h^T n) dz + (A_0 x, x) + (BG_e^* Cx, x) \\ &= (A_0 x, x) + (BG_e^* Cx, x) \end{aligned}$$

Assume $b_i = c_i$ or $B^* = C$ and $G_e^* \equiv -g_e^* < 0$.

Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} (A_c x, x) &= (A_0 x, x) + (BG_e^* Cx, x) \\ &= (A_0 x, x) - g_e^* (Cx, B^* x) \\ &= (A_0 x, x) - g_e^* \|Cx\|^2 \\ &\leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

which implies

$$\text{Re}(A_c x, x) = (A_0 x, x) - g_e^* \|Cx\|^2 \quad \text{and} \quad B^* = C$$

which is *not* quite strictly dissipative.

But we have the following result:

Theorem 2: A_c has compact resolvent; hence it has discrete spectrum, in the sense that it consists only of isolated eigenvalues with finite multiplicity.

Proof: See Appendix I.

Consider that

$X = E_s \oplus E_u$ where E_s is the stable eigenspace and E_u is the unstable eigenspace with corresponding projections P_s, P_u . Assume that

$\dim E_u \equiv N_u$ and $E_u^\perp = E$. This implies that

P_s, P_u are bounded self adjoint operators.

Choose $C \equiv P_u$; this is possible when the unstable subspace is finite-dimensional.

Then we have the following result:

Theorem 3:

$$\text{Re}(A_0 x, x) \leq -\alpha \|P_s x\|^2 \quad \text{for all } x \in D(A)$$

implies that (A, B, C) is almost strictly dissipative (ASD).

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned}
\operatorname{Re}(A_c x, x) &= \operatorname{Re}(A x, x) - g_e^* \|C x\|^2 \\
&= \operatorname{Re}(A_0 x, x) - g_e^* \|C x\|^2 \\
&\leq -\alpha \|P_s x\|^2 - g_e^* \|P_u x\|^2 \\
&\leq -\alpha \left(\|P_s x\|^2 + \|P_u x\|^2 \right) \\
&= -\alpha \|x\|^2
\end{aligned}$$

by choosing $g_e^* \geq \alpha$.

Therefore, $\operatorname{Re}(A_c x, x) \leq -\alpha \|x\|^2$ and $C = B^*$ implies that there exists

$$G_e^* \equiv -g_e^* < 0 \text{ such that}$$

$(A_c = A + B G_e^* C, B, C)$ is strictly dissipative with $P = I$.

Here is a simple first order symmetric hyperbolic system example to illustrate some of the above:

$$\begin{cases} x_t = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{A_1} x_z + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{A_0} x + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}}_B (u + u_D) \\ y = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_C x \end{cases}$$

where $\varepsilon > 0$ is small.

If we use

$$G_e^* = -g_* < 0$$

this implies that

$$\begin{aligned}
\operatorname{Re}(A_c x, x) &= (A_0 x, x) - g_*^* \|C x\|^2 \\
&= -\varepsilon \|q_1\|^2 - g_*^* \|q_2\|^2 \\
&\leq -\underbrace{\min(g_*, \varepsilon)}_{\alpha > 0} \left(\|q_1\|^2 + \|q_2\|^2 \right) \\
&\leq -\alpha \|x\|^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } x \equiv \begin{bmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then $(A_c = A + B G_e^* C, B, C)$ is strictly dissipative with $P = I$ and we can apply Theo. 4 which is proved later.

V. ROBUSTNESS OF THE ERROR SYSTEM

We consider the definition of Strict Dissipativity for infinite-dimensional systems and the general form of the ‘‘adaptive error system’’ to later prove stability. The main theorem of this section will be utilized in the following section to assess the stability of the adaptive controller with disturbance rejection for linear diffusion systems.

Noting that there can be some ambiguity in the literature with the definition of strictly dissipative systems, we modify the suggestion of Wen in [8] for finite dimensional systems and expand it to include infinite dimensional systems.

Definition 1: The triple (A_c, B, C) is said to be **Strictly Dissipative** if A_c is a densely defined, closed operator on $D(A_c) \subseteq X$ a complex Hilbert space with inner product (x, y) and corresponding norm $\|x\| \equiv \sqrt{(x, x)}$ and generates a C_0 semigroup of bounded operators $U(t)$, and (B, C) are bounded finite rank input/output operators with rank M where $B : R^m \rightarrow X$ and $C : X \rightarrow R^m$. In addition there exist symmetric positive bounded operator P on X such that $p_{\min} \|x\|^2 \leq (P x, x) \leq p_{\max} \|x\|^2$, i.e. P is bounded and coercive, and

$$\begin{cases} \operatorname{Re}(P A_c e, e) \equiv \frac{1}{2} [(P A_c e, e) + (e, P A_c e)] \\ \leq -\alpha \|e\|^2 \\ P B = C^* \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $\alpha > 0$ and $e \in D(A_c)$.

We also say that (A, B, C) is *Almost Strictly Dissipative (ASD)* when there exists a $G_* \in \mathfrak{R}^{m \times m}$ such that (A_c, B, C) is strictly dissipative with $A_c \equiv A + B G_* C$.

Note that if $P = I$ in (11), by the Lumer-Phillips Theorem [11], p405, we would have $\|U_c(t)\| \leq e^{-\alpha t}$; $t \geq 0$.

The following theorem shows that convergence to a neighborhood with radius determined by the supremum norm of v is possible for a specific type of adaptive error system.

In the following, we denote $\|M\|_2 \equiv \sqrt{\operatorname{tr}(M \gamma^{-1} M^T)}$ as the trace norm of a matrix M where $\gamma > 0$.

Theorem 4: Consider the coupled system of differential equations

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial e}{\partial t} = A_c e + B \underbrace{(G(t) - G^*)}_{\Delta G} z + v \\ e_y = C e \\ \dot{G}(t) = -e_y z^T \gamma - a G(t) \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $e, v \in D(A_c)$, $z \in R^m$ and $\begin{bmatrix} e \\ G \end{bmatrix} \in \bar{X} \equiv X \times R^{m \times m}$

is a Hilbert space with

$$\text{inner product } \left(\begin{bmatrix} e_1 \\ G_1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} e_2 \\ G_2 \end{bmatrix} \right) \equiv (e_1, e_2) + \text{tr}(G_1 \gamma^{-1} G_2),$$

$$\text{norm } \left\| \begin{bmatrix} e \\ G \end{bmatrix} \right\| \equiv \left(\|e\|^2 + \text{tr}(G \gamma^{-1} G) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ and where } G(t) \text{ is}$$

the $m \times m$ adaptive gain matrix and γ is any positive definite constant matrix, each of appropriate dimension. Assume the following:

i.) (A, B, C) is ASD with $A_c \equiv A + B G_* C$

ii.) there exists $M_G > 0$ such that

$$\sqrt{\text{tr}(G^* G^{*T})} \leq M_G$$

iii.) there exists $M_v > 0$ such that

$$\sup_{t \geq 0} \|v(t)\| \leq M_v < \infty$$

iv.) there exists $\alpha > 0$ such that $a \leq \frac{\alpha}{p_{\max}}$, where

$p_{\max}$ is defined in Definition 1

v.) the positive definite matrix γ satisfies

$$\text{tr}(\gamma^{-1}) \leq \left(\frac{M_v}{a M_G} \right)^2,$$

then the gain matrix, $G(t)$, is bounded, and the state, $e(t)$ exponentially with rate e^{-at} approaches the ball of radius

$$R_* \equiv \frac{(1 + \sqrt{p_{\max}})}{a \sqrt{p_{\min}}} M_v$$

Proof of Theorem 4: See Appendix 2.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In Theorem 4 we have a robustness result for adaptive control under the hypothesis of almost strict dissipativity for infinite dimensional systems. This idea is an extension of the concept of m-accretivity for infinite dimensional systems; see [9] pp278-280. In Theo. 4, we showed that adaptive regulation to a neighborhood was possible with an adaptive controller modified with a leakage term. This controller also mitigates persistent disturbances and output tracks a finite dimensional reference model. We can relax the requirement that the disturbance enters through the same channels as the control.

We applied these results to general symmetric hyperbolic systems using m actuator and m sensors and adaptive output feedback. We showed that under some limitations on operator spectrum that we can accomplish robust adaptive control. This allows the possibility of rather simple direct adaptive control which also mitigates persistent disturbances for a large class of applications in wave behavior, electromagnetic fields, and some quantum fields.

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APPENDIX 1

Proof of Theorem 2.

We will **assume** the operator A is closed. If not we can work with the closure of A . It is easy to see that A is skew self-adjoint, i.e. $(Af, g) = -(f, Ag)$ for all

$f, g \in D(A)$. Therefore the spectrum of A must lie on the imaginary axis and any complex $\lambda \in \rho(A)$ if it has nonzero real part.

With coercive boundary conditions, it can be shown that for all $x \in D(A)$, we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \left\| \frac{\partial x}{\partial z_i} \right\|^2 \leq K^2 \left(\|Ax\|^2 + \|x\|^2 \right)$$

and so $D(A) \subseteq H^1$.

Let $\lambda \in \rho(A)$, the resolvent set of A and consider the resolvent operator

$$R(\lambda) \equiv (\lambda I - A)^{-1} : X = L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow D(A)$$

We want to show that this resolvent operator is (sequentially) compact:

Take a bounded sequence

$$\{x_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty} \subseteq X \text{ and define } h_k \equiv R(1)x_k \in D(A).$$

$$\text{Then } \sum_{i=1}^N \left\| \frac{\partial h_k}{\partial z_i} \right\|^2 \leq K^2 \left(\|Ah_k\|^2 + \|h_k\|^2 \right).$$

$$\text{But } h_k - Ah_k = x_k \text{ or } Ah_k = h_k - x_k$$

which implies

$$\|Ah_k\|^2 = \|h_k - x_k\|^2 \leq (\|h_k\| + \|x_k\|)^2.$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \|h_k\|_1^2 &\equiv \|h_k\|^2 + \sum_{i=1}^N \left\| \frac{\partial h_k}{\partial z_i} \right\|^2 \\ &\leq \|h_k\|^2 + K^2 \left(\|Ah_k\|^2 + \|h_k\|^2 \right) \\ &\leq \|h_k\|^2 + K^2 \left((\|h_k\| + \|x_k\|)^2 + \|h_k\|^2 \right) \\ &= (1 + K^2) \|h_k\|^2 + K^2 \left(\|h_k\| + \|x_k\| \right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

Now $\{x_k\}$ is bounded by assumption and

$h_k \equiv R(1)x_k$ is bounded because $R(1)$ is a bounded operator.

Therefore, $\|h_k\|_1$ is a bounded and so $\{h_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ is a bounded sequence in H_1 .

Consequently by the Rellich Compactness Theorem (see e.g [19]Theo. 8.38 p175 or [20] Theo. 2 p246),

H^1 is compactly embedded in $X \equiv L^2(\Omega)$ because Ω is a bounded open set with smooth boundary.

Therefore there exists a convergent subsequence of $\{h_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ in $X \equiv L^2(\Omega)$ and the resolvent operator

$R(1) = (I - A)^{-1}$ is a compact operator. Then, by Theo. 6.29 [9]p187, $R(\lambda)$ is compact for all $\lambda \in \rho(A)$ and the spectrum is discrete, in the sense that it consists only of isolated eigenvalues with finite multiplicities.

End of Proof.

APPENDIX 2

First we note that if see [10] Theo 8.8 p 151. Consider the positive definite function,

$$V = \frac{1}{2}(Pe, e) + \frac{1}{2} \text{tr}[\Delta G \gamma^{-1} \Delta G^T]$$

where $\Delta G(t) \equiv G(t) - G^*$ and P satisfies (11). Taking the time derivative (we assume this can be done in X) and substituting (12) into the result yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} &= \frac{1}{2}[(PA_c e, e) + (e, PA_c e)] + (PBw, e) \\ &\quad + \text{tr}[\Delta \dot{G} \gamma^{-1} \Delta G^T] + (Pe, v) \end{aligned}$$

where $w \equiv \Delta Gz$. Invoking the equalities in the definition of Strict Dissipativity using $x^T y = \text{tr}[yx^T]$, and substituting (12) into the last expression

(with $(PBw, e) = (w, Ce) = \langle e_y, w \rangle \equiv e_y^* w$), we obtain

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned}
\dot{V} &= \text{Re}(PA_c e, e) + \langle e_y, w \rangle \\
&\quad - a \cdot \text{tr} [G \gamma^{-1} \Delta G^T] \\
&\quad - \underbrace{\text{tr}(e_y z^T \Delta G^T)}_{\langle e_y, w \rangle} + (Pe, v) \\
&\leq -\|e\|^2 - a \cdot \text{tr} [(\Delta G + G^*) \gamma^{-1} \Delta G^T] \\
&\quad + (Pe, v) \\
&\leq -\left(\alpha \|e\|^2 + a \cdot \text{tr} [\Delta G \gamma^{-1} \Delta G^T] \right) \\
&\quad + a \cdot \left| \text{tr} [G^* \gamma^{-1} \Delta G^T] \right| + |(Pe, v)| \\
&\leq -\left(\frac{2\alpha}{p_{\min}} \bullet \frac{1}{2} (Pe, e) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + 2a \bullet \frac{1}{2} \text{tr} [\Delta G \gamma^{-1} \Delta G^T] \right) \\
&\quad + a \cdot \left| \text{tr} [G^* \gamma^{-1} \Delta G^T] \right| + |(Pe, v)| \\
&\leq -2aV + a \cdot \left| \text{tr} [G^* \gamma^{-1} \Delta G^T] \right| + |(Pe, v)|
\end{aligned} \right.$$

Now, using the Cauchy-Schwartz Inequality

$$\left| \text{tr} [G^* \gamma^{-1} \Delta G^T] \right| \leq \|G^*\|_2 \|\Delta G\|_2$$

And

$$|(Pe, v)| \leq \left\| P^{\frac{1}{2}} v \right\| \left\| P^{\frac{1}{2}} e \right\| = \sqrt{(Pv, v)} \bullet \sqrt{(Pe, e)}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{V} + 2aV &\leq a \cdot \|G^*\|_2 \|\Delta G\|_2 + \sqrt{p_{\max}} \|v\| \sqrt{(Pe, e)} \\
&\leq a \cdot \|G^*\|_2 \|\Delta G\|_2 + (\sqrt{p_{\max}} M_v) \sqrt{(Pe, e)} \\
&\leq \left(a \|G^*\|_2 + \sqrt{p_{\max}} M_v \right) \sqrt{2} \underbrace{\left[\frac{1}{2} (Pe, e) + \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta G\|_2^2 \right]}_{\frac{1}{V^{\frac{1}{2}}}}
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\dot{V} + 2aV}{V^{\frac{1}{2}}} \leq a \left(\|G^*\|_2 + \sqrt{p_{\max}} M_v \right) \sqrt{2}$$

Now, using the identity $\text{tr} [ABC] = \text{tr} [CAB]$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\|G^*\|_2 &\equiv \left[\text{tr} (G^* \gamma^{-1} (G^*)^T) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left[\text{tr} ((G^*)^T G^* \gamma^{-1}) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&\leq \left[\left(\text{tr} ((G^*)^T G^* (G^*)^T G^*) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\text{tr} (\gamma^{-1} \gamma^{-1}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&= \left[\text{tr} (G^* (G^*)^T) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\text{tr} (\gamma^{-1}) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&\leq \frac{M_v}{a M_G} \bullet M_G = \frac{M_v}{a}
\end{aligned}$$

which implies

$$\frac{\dot{V} + 2aV}{V^{\frac{1}{2}}} \leq \left(1 + \sqrt{p_{\max}} \right) M_v \sqrt{2} \quad (13)$$

From

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d}{dt} (2e^{at} V^{\frac{1}{2}}) &= e^{at} \frac{\dot{V} + 2aV}{V^{\frac{1}{2}}} \\
&\leq e^{at} \left(1 + \sqrt{p_{\max}} \right) M_v \sqrt{2}
\end{aligned}$$

Integrating this expression we have:

$$e^{at} V(t)^{1/2} - V(0)^{1/2} \leq \frac{\left(1 + \sqrt{p_{\max}} \right) M_v}{a} (e^{at} - 1)$$

Therefore,

$$V(t)^{1/2} \leq V(0)^{1/2} e^{-at} + \frac{\left(1 + \sqrt{p_{\max}} \right) M_v}{a} (1 - e^{-at}) \quad (14)$$

The function $V(t)$ is a norm function of the state $e(t)$ and matrix $G(t)$. So, since $V(t)^{1/2}$ is bounded for all t , then $e(t)$ and $G(t)$ are bounded. We also obtain the following inequality:

$$\sqrt{p_{\min}} \|e(t)\| \leq V(t)^{1/2}$$

Substitution of this into (14) gives us an exponential bound on state $e(t)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\|e(t)\| &\leq \frac{e^{-at}}{\sqrt{p_{\min}}} V(0)^{1/2} \\
&\quad + \frac{\left(1 + \sqrt{p_{\max}} \right) M_v}{a \sqrt{p_{\min}}} (1 - e^{-at})
\end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Taking the limit superior of (15), we have

$$\overline{\lim}_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \|e(t)\| \leq \frac{\left(1 + \sqrt{p_{\max}} \right)}{a \sqrt{p_{\min}}} M_v \equiv R_* \quad \text{End of Proof.}$$